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Multi-modal Imaging for Porosity Quantification in Partially-impregnated UD Woven Glass Fiber/ Polypropylene Composites

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CONTEXT

Compression Flow Molding

Processing conditions

Impregnation

Fiber-bed Deformation + Flow Resistance

Compaction

(TexGen -MICRA); (Binetruy *et al.*, 2015)

Inter-bundle

Inter-fiber

- Inter-bundle Porosity
- Inter-fiber Porosity

Objective: To identify a correlation between localization of residual porosity with the **compaction ratio** as a processing control parameter?

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Reinforcement

- UD Woven GF
- 6 GF plies; $[0/90]_3$
- Areal weight – 1054 g.m^{-2}

Thermoplastic Film

- PP (Total, PPC13442)
- 7 PP films; 0,53 mm thick/ film
- MFI (100 g/ 10 min)

Manufacturing – Pinette Press (120KN)

CORRELATIVE IMAGING TECHNIQUE

Raw images (meso-scale)

Stitching

Extended field images (macro-scale)

Synthetic images

Artefact filtering
Intensity correction

Registration

QUALITATIVE RESULTS

0° oriented fiber bundles - Macro Scale

- Meso Scale

- Micro Scale

QUANTITATIVE RESULTS

Intra bundle area percentages

CONCLUSIONS

- ▶ Multi-modal imaging helps in the localization of residual porosity and PP within partially-impregnated fiber bundles.
- ▶ Correlative imaging enhances the accuracy of quantification of impregnation quality.

PERSPECTIVES

- ▶ Extending the approach to μ -CT data.
- ▶ Validation of correlative imaging approach for impregnation analysis in the context of **CRTM process**.